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OVERSTRIKING AND REMINTING IN THE ROMAN PRINCIPATE:
A GENERAL FRAMEWORK AND SOME CASE STUDIES
IN THE PROVINCIAL COINAGE

Abstract – This paper provides a general outline of the phenomena of overstriking and reminting in the Early and High Roman Empire, with a special emphasis on provincial coinage. Overstriking seems to have been rare in the provinces; it had several different purposes: e.g., the renewal of Roman provincial coins worn out through prolonged circulation; the conversion of foreign coins circulating in newly annexed territory into Roman ones; the sporadic (and locally circumscribed) obliteration of civic bronze coins produced under emperors who had fallen victim to damnatio memoriae.

APAPER LIKE THE PRESENT ONE, which sets out to provide a general overview over a vast subject, calls for brief introductory remarks pertaining to methodological issues. When ancient authorities, for whatever reason, did not want certain coins within their area of jurisdiction to go on circulating – at least in the condition these pieces were in at that time –, they had basically three options for action. The most radical option was to recall or withhold the coins in question, melt them down and issue new coins from their metal. Alternatively, if authorities wanted to restrike the metal, but preferred to circumvent the laborious task of producing new planchets,^[1] the coins deemed unfit for further circulation could be used as flans and simply be overstruck with new types; in this way, the original types disappeared more or less completely at least on the majority of the restruck coins, provided that the technical standards of the operation of restriking were sufficiently high. Finally, when even the production of new dies was to be avoided, a quicker and cheaper solution was not to change the entire design of the coins, but to merely supplement or alter it; this was an option frequently chosen in the world of Roman provincial coinage.

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^[1] In a technological perspective, the preparation of flans was the most complex step in the production of coins, see Woytek forthcoming A.

The common way of doing so was of course to countermark the coins. Normally, countermarking was performed with small punches bearing an image or some letters;^[2] in one famous case, a posthumous issue of bronzes produced in the name of the *archiereus* of the *koinon Asias* Alexandros Kleon of Sardis, honouring Germanicus († AD 19) and Drusus minor († AD 23),^[3] elaborate ring-shaped punches were used to restrike just the legends of both sides of the coins. While the obverse legend was overstruck with the very same text,^[4] the reverse legend (originally containing the name of Alexandros Kleon) was changed to feature the name of the proconsul of Asia in the dative case: ΓΑΙΩ ΑΣΙΝΝΙΩ ΠΩΛΛΙΩΝΙ ΑΝΘΥΠΑΤΩ.^[5] The majority of these pieces have come down to us in this curiously overstruck form (fig. 1).

Fig. 1 – Sardis, bronze, ‘countermarked’ in the name of the proconsul C. Asinius Pollio. *RPC I*, 2995. Naumann 53 (71V/2017), 53 (10.89 g – 27 mm)

When part of the design of an issue was considered offensive – for example the imperial portrait, or a name in the legend, in the case of a *damnatio memoriae* –, the respective part was sometimes also removed from the coins manually, piece by piece.^[6] This procedure is to be observed occasionally in the provincial material. Thus, such coins became monuments-in-miniature to the damnation of a person’s memory, and the continued circulation of these disfigured pieces was of course much more exemplary and deterrent than simply to melt down the issues in question: the latter measure is attested for the imperial coinage in a few passages of our literary sources.^[7]

From the point of view of ancient authorities reminting, overstriking and countermarking were closely related procedures: to some extent they are all methods of coinage renewal. For the modern numismatist, by contrast, the difference between the three measures could not be greater: while counter-

[2] The standard work on Greek imperial countermarks is Howgego 1985.

[3] *RPC I*, 2994–2995. On this issue, see also Tameanko 1999.

[4] On this side of the coins, the overstriking apparently just had technical reasons.

[5] In *RPC I*, p. 488 the overstriking is dated to c. AD 28/29; traditionally, the proconsulship of Asinius Pollio had been dated to AD 38/39 or 39/40: see Stumpf 1991, p. 136–138.

[6] For a well-illustrated recent overview, see Calomino 2016, especially ch. II–V, p. 44–153.

[7] See Wolters 1999, p. 150–161, most notably on Cass. Dio 60.22.3, where a decree of the Senate, enacted under Claudius in AD 43, to melt down all the bronze coins with the portrait of Caligula is reported. On this episode, see also the remarks by Flower 2006, p. 157 (with further bibliography).

marked coins are especially easy to spot, and comprehensive operations of restriking, even if carried out with the utmost care and technical competence, are bound to leave traces of the undertypes at least on a few of the coins concerned, reminting completely extinguishes the issues in question. Large-scale reminting of precious metal coinage can potentially be detected through metallurgical analyses, but their results are not always unequivocal, and the types of the coins that were melted down are irrevocably lost. Hence, reminting is one of the most important factors determining the life-span of various types of coinages and the quantities in which they are available for study in the modern period, as Ann Johnston reminded us in her article on Roman provincials entitled “Questions of Survival”.^[8] While we will discuss some potential episodes of reminting in our survey, we will not be dealing with countermarking.^[9] The main focus of this paper will, however, be on overstriking.

Overstrikes have different degrees of importance for different areas of research in ancient numismatics. In fields where absolute and relative chronology are notoriously problematic, for example in archaic and classical Greek as well as in Roman Republican numismatics, the study of overstrikes is obviously among the prime tools of the numismatist, and research on overstruck coins of these series has a long and distinguished history. Roman coins of the imperial period are different, in many respects. Firstly, in a general perspective, problems of chronology are minimal in imperial coinage, as compared to other areas of numismatics: the imperial portraits provide a rough absolute chronology for the vast majority of these coins – except for the so-called pseudo-autonomous issues of the East –, and in many cases the emperors’ titulatures on the coins even allow a fairly precise dating of the series. Hence, by and large there is no need to look out for overstrikes in order to establish the date of Roman imperial issues; we might just hope to perhaps be able to adjust the fine chronology of some series with their help. That we do not have to rely on them is very fortunate: as is well known, with a few notable exceptions – some of which will be discussed in detail in this article or in other contributions to this volume –, Roman ‘imperial’ and ‘provincial’ overstrikes of the Principate (and early Dominate) are extremely rare. It is necessary to sketch out the basic reasons for this, before we can look at a few case studies among the episodes of reminting and overstriking attested in provincial contexts.

Let us start from the observation that enormous amounts of silver coinage were produced by the Roman state between the mid-second century BC and

^[8] Johnston 1998.

^[9] For an authoritative overview over the many different motivations to countermark issues, including updating the emperor’s titulature, changing the denomination of a coin, confirming coins in circulation or commemorating an imperial visit or victory, see Howgego 1985, p. 4-7.

the Civil Wars in the transitional phase between Republic and Empire. According to an apparently well-founded estimate published around twenty years ago, the pool of Roman denarii in circulation increased between five- and ten-fold between 157 and 50 BC alone^[10] – and then there was another drastic surge in coin-output, in the two following decades, when the Caesarian and post-Caesarian Civil Wars took place.^[11]

These Roman Republican coins were extremely long-lived in circulation: pre-imperial silver denarii were used into the imperial period in large numbers and made up a significant quantity of the silver in Roman hoards in the first and even second centuries AD.^[12] Mark Antony's legionary denarii, produced in the run-up to the battle of Actium from a baser silver alloy of just around 83% on average,^[13] circulated even until the third century AD in some areas. The appallingly worn pre-imperial denarii in hoards of the Principate are fitting symbols of a basic systemic deficiency in the monetary economy of the Roman state: ever since the epochal creation of the denarius coinage during the Second Punic War, before 211 BC, the Romans had failed to devise a strategy for renewing their silver coinage. Apparently, they simply kept producing coins – especially denarii –, thereby continuously adding to the pool of coinage: this increase in the quantity of Roman (silver) coinage went hand in hand with the eventual growth of the area of circulation of the Roman currency and with the intensification of coin-based economic transactions, prompted by what has been termed 'economic growth' in the course of the late Republican period.^[14] However, as time went on, these coins lost more and more of their weight through wear. As has recently been observed, by the early Principate the gradual deterioration of the masses of old Republican silver coins in circulation may have threatened to destabilise the Roman monetary system; it first seems to have led to slight metrological adaptations of the newly produced imperial currency, until Nero, in AD 64, proceeded to a groundbreaking reform of the gold and silver coinage, which appears to have triggered the first major coinage renewal of the denarius period.^[15] As Kevin Butcher and this author have argued, it seems that the one literary source describing a major coinage renewal in the early Roman Empire – the famous sentence preserved in an excerpt from Cassius Dio stating that Trajan "melted down all the worn coinage"^[16] – should be viewed in the context of

[10] Lockyear 1999, p. 242 (with fig. 13).

[11] See Woytek forthcoming b.

[12] For notable recent examples, see Ireland 2013 (a British hoard closing under Nero in AD 63/4: 1,153 silver coins, of which 812 struck before 27 BC) and Dembski & Zavadil 2004 (an Austrian hoard closing late under Hadrian: 7 aurei and 1,261 denarii and drachms, of which 853 are pre-imperial). For Britain, see also the classic paper by Reece 1988, p. 91-94.

[13] For a few new analyses of denarii of the series RRC 544, see Butcher & Ponting 2014, p. 161f.

[14] See Kay 2014, p. 321-325.

[15] Butcher & Ponting 2014, p. 434-460.

[16] Cass. Dio 68.15.3¹ (vol. 3, p. 201 Boissevain): τὸ τε νόμισμα πᾶν τὸ ἐξίτηλον συνεχώνευσε.

Nero's monetary measures: renewing the denarius coinage that had accrued in the empire for more than two centuries must have been an enormous enterprise that could well have taken more than a generation. Hence, the reign of Trajan (98-117) may have seen a preliminary completion of the coinage renewal started under the last Julio-Claudian emperor.^[17] By the second half of the second century AD, virtually no denarii coined prior to Nero's reform were left in circulation, except for the anomalous legionary denarii of Antony.

The standards chosen by Nero for his new gold and silver coinage were different from the Republican (or Caesarian and Augustan) ones: he reduced the weight of the aureus to $\frac{1}{45}$ of a Roman pound (*libra*); the weight of the denarius – which had been struck at $\frac{1}{84}$ pound during the Late Republic – to $\frac{1}{96}$ of a Roman pound; and the alloy of the denarius, which used to be of almost pure silver, to initially just 80% of silver.^[18] Hence, it is easy to understand that the major coinage renewal starting under Nero of course had to be operated by means of melting down the old and worn aurei and denarii of higher standards – as we also learn from the sentence from Cassius Dio just cited –, and by subsequently re-using their metal in the form of new flans, not by means of overstriking the old coins.

It is also for this reason that practically no Roman imperial denarii of the first and second centuries AD overstruck on earlier coins are known. Most of the imperial silver coins of the early to high Principate reported or suspected to be overstrikes turn out to be simply double-struck with the same dies. In 1940, C.H.V. Sutherland published a denarius of Galba produced at a Spanish mint that shows traces of an undertype comprising the letters RO on the reverse. He claimed that the coin, kept in the Ashmolean Museum in Oxford, documented deliberate overstriking of Neronian denarii by officials of Galba in Spain,^[19] much in the same way as Allotte de la Fuÿe, in one of the classic papers on the subject in a global perspective, had explained the clearly identifiable overstrike of a tetradrachm bearing the portraits of Antony and Cleopatra by the Parthian king of kings Phraates IV (38-2 BC) as a purely politically motivated restrike and as a “mutilation intentionnelle” of his enemies' ‘heads’.^[20] However, Sutherland's interpretation of the Oxford denarius may safely be discarded: recent re-examination of the piece by Dorian Bocciarelli has revealed that this is not a Nero overstrike at all, but merely an overstrike of another Galba denarius of the same Spanish mint, with a different reverse type and the accompanying legend ROMA RENASC, part of which is still visible on the coin today.^[21] The piece may have been restruck

[17] Butcher & Woytek forthcoming; cp. Butcher & Ponting 2014, p. 226.

[18] Butcher & Ponting 2014, p. 201-238, esp. p. 217-219.

[19] Sutherland 1940, p. 266.

[20] See Allotte de la Fuÿe 1904, p. 187 (with pl. 6, no. 3). The undertype: *RPC* I, 4094.

[21] Undertype: cp. *RIC* I² Galba 57; overtyp: *RIC* I² Galba 52 var. (orientation of reverse legend) = Sutherland 1984, p. 172, no. 52a. For details, see Bocciarelli forthcoming.

merely by accident, or because it was originally badly centred, or for another mundane reason, much like some of the Roman Republican denarius overstrikes that are attested.^[22]

‘True’ overstrikes of Roman imperial silver coins over Roman denarii occur only in the third century AD, after the Roman monetary system had undergone profound change through the introduction of a new denomination: the radiate – often called ‘antoninianus’ in numismatics –, which replaced the denarius as the standard silver coin from AD 238 onwards. For Trajan Decius (249–251) and Trebonianus Gallus (251–253) numerous overstrikes of such antoniniani on older, mostly Severan denarii are attested.^[23] Recently, an early radiate of Valerianus I (253–260) from the mint of Rome turned up, overstruck on a denarius of Severus Alexander (222–235; fig. 2).^[24]

Fig. 2 – Valerianus I, antoninianus, Rome (overstruck on denarius of Severus Alexander). Göbl 2000, 25d (undertype: RIC IV.2, Severus Alexander 254).
Leu Numismatik AG, Web Auction 1 (25/VI/2017), 1187 (2.65 g – ↑↓)

scale 200%

^[22] See the updated listing in the contribution by Andrew McCabe to this volume.

^[23] See, most notably, Mattingly 1939, p. 41–46 (in his comments on the overstrikes observed in the Dorchester hoard) and Callu 1969, pp. 242 and 257. The overstruck piece published by Michon 1987 is correctly identified as a contemporary forgery by the author. — The overstrikes attested for a group of radiates produced at the mint of Antioch under Gordian III (238–244) are a separate phenomenon (overstriking of a group of antoniniani for which we may suspect the use of a faulty obverse die): see van Heesch 1993, p. 28.

^[24] The antoninianus type of Valerianus: IOVI CONSERVA; the denarius undertype: SPES PVBLICA.

When the usurper Regalianus had antoniniani struck for himself and his wife Dryantilla around the year 260, in a makeshift mint set up at Carnuntum, the capital of the province Pannonia superior – where recently one coin each of Regalianus and Dryantilla were found in controlled archaeological excavations^[25] –, no flans were produced for their coins at all, but the entire issue was overstruck: almost without exception on denarii dating to the period from Septimius Severus (193-211) to Pupienus (238).^[26]

What about the bronze coinage? As with the silver, imperial bronze overstrikes of the Principate from official mints are very rare:^[27] a middle bronze of Domitian (81-96) is unusual on more than one count, since it is struck from dupondius dies (with a radiate crown), but overstruck on a copper as issued under Claudius (41-54), in the name of Germanicus.^[28] The undertype of an as of Nerva (96-98) in the Verona coin cabinet is even older: an Augustan moneyer's as from the mint of Rome (fig. 3).

Fig. 3 – Nerva, as, Rome (overstruck on Augustan moneyer's as).
Rev. type LIBERTAS PVBLICA (end of obv. legend illegible).
Verona, Schmidt-Dick 1995, p. 302, no. 5773 (9.66 g – ↑↓)

Such a chronological gap between undertype and oertype is exceptional. One of two overstruck asses of Caracalla (211-217) presented in a paper by S. Michon has been identified as an overstrike over Commodus (177-192).^[29] However, official imperial bronze overstrikes tend to be overstrikes of other coins of the same emperor: they are attested, e.g., for Nero,^[30] Trajan,^[31]

^[25] See Găzdac 2012, p. 25f.

^[26] See Dembski, Winter & Woytek 2007, p. 547-549.

^[27] Komnick 2001, p. 143 lists only two pertinent specimens for which he could identify the undertypes.

^[28] Carradice 1981.

^[29] See Michon 1988. For another case of a third-century bronze overstrike on a coin of a predecessor, see Callu 1969, p. 119 (Valerianus on Volusianus).

^[30] Giard 1988, p. 161, no. 383: dupondius, Paris, temple of Janus, overstruck on a dupondius featuring Roma seated to the left. I am grateful to Andrew Burnett for pointing out this coin to me.

^[31] E.g. Woytek 2010A, vol. 1, p. 425, no. 474v²: as, Berlin, Trajan's column, overstruck on a DACIA AVGVST PROVINCIA middle bronze (illustrated in vol. 2, plate 96).

Hadrian,^[32] and Gordian III,^[33] and it is very likely that all these pieces were overstruck before they had left the mint.

The numerically most important group of bronze overstrikes of the Principate, however, are contemporary imitations: overstriking had been playing an important role in the production of imitative coinages in Italy since the Republican period,^[34] and, curiously, some early imperial issues of imitations from Gaul were also produced by overstriking official coins.^[35] While the economic logic leading to these overstrikes is not immediately apparent, it is evident in another case: Pierre Bastien has demonstrated that the overstrikes of so-called ‘double sestertii’ of Postumus, showing the emperor with a radiate crown, on sestertii of the High Empire, were produced by “ateliers irréguliers”; the coin forgers evidently made a profit by doubling the face value of these coins.^[36] Hence, the scope of this unofficial wave of overstriking in the Western empire in the third century is somewhat reminiscent of the best-documented episode of overstriking of the Early Dominate, dating from the years after Constantine the Great’s reform of the billon-currency in AD 318, in which the nummus was re-tariffed at 25 denarii of account. In that phase earlier pieces struck by Constantine, as well as nummi produced by his rival Licinius in the east, who maintained the old exchange rate of 12.5 denarii (and advertised this on the reverse of his coins) were restruck by Constantinian mints, mainly at Arles. By restriking these pieces, the Constantinian administration doubled their face-value.^[37] The motivation for these overstrikes thus was an economic, not a political one.

This, then, is the imperial backdrop against which various episodes of overstriking and reminting in the provincial coinage have to be interpreted. Before we examine some case studies related to overstriking in the provinces, we shall discuss some (potential) episodes of large-scale reminting. These episodes are most interesting from the economic historian’s point of view; however, as will become apparent, they are often very problematic, since the definite evidence provided by overstrikes over the original coins is, by definition, lacking.

[32] *BMC III*, Hadrian 1754 note (dupondius, British Museum, reg. no. 1934,1018.26: ex L.A. Lawrence). For an imperial overstrike of a Hadrian bronze, see already Froelich 1737, p. 437 (with illustration).

[33] Leukel 1986.

[34] Cp. Stannard 1998 and the contribution by Stannard to this volume.

[35] See, e.g., the articles by Labrousse 1977 and Gricourt 1985. To this group, the middle bronze Elsen 136 (24/III/2018), no. 91 (8.99 g), which is misdescribed in the auction catalogue, may be added. The material seems to be copious.

[36] Bastien 1967, pp. 30, 91f. and 223–225, plates 62–65.

[37] On this episode of overstriking, which has been investigated since the 1960s, see the overview by Wienand 2012, pp. 301f. (with exhaustive bibliography) and 344–348. Two of the relevant publications of overstruck nummi are by Brenot & Rogers 1978 and Amandry & Brenot 1980.

The first case concerns the province of Egypt and must be viewed in the context of Nero's reforms of the imperial precious metal coinages described above. In Egypt, there was an enormous output of rather base billon tetradrachms in the final phase of Nero's government, during his regnal years 10-14 (AD 63/64 to 67/68). In this period, the mint must have been working under considerable pressure to meet the demand for new coins, which is also evident from minting mistakes: brockages and occasional overstrikes over tetradrachms of Nero himself are especially common in this last phase of his coinage.^[38] Compare a tetradrachm of year 14 with the bust of ΗΡΑ ΑΡΓΕΙΑ on the reverse in fig. 4; this coin was overstruck on a tetradrachm featuring ΑΚΤΙΟΣ ΑΠΟΛΛΩΝ (a type produced from year 13 onwards), and part of this legend as well as Apollo's head and his quiver are still clearly in evidence on the coin.

*Fig. 4 – Nero, tetradrachm, Alexandria in Egypt, year 14 (overstruck on tetradrachm of Nero of the same mint with a bust of Aktios Apollon).
RPC I, 5315 (undertype: RPC I, 5301, 5311 or 5317). CNG Triton 21
(9/11/2018; ex Staffieri coll.), 19 (12.92 g – ↑↑ – 25 mm)*

scale 200%

^[38] RPC I, p. 704 (with references to Christiansen 1988); for a brockage of this period see also Savio 1988, pp. 227 and 237 (cp. also p. 225, note 14). Savio 1988, pp. 225 and 227 also publishes two earlier overstrikes of tetradrachms of Nero's years 4 and 5 on tetradrachms of his year 4.

In Nero's year 13 (AD 66/67), two of the eleven reverse images used for his tetradrachm coinage are remarkable and have been interpreted as typological indicators of an important operation of reminting under this emperor: the right-facing heads of the radiate Divus Augustus (ΘΕΟΣ ΣΕΒΑΣΤΟΣ, *RPC I*, 5294) and of the laureate Tiberius (ΤΙΒΕΡΙΟΣ ΚΑΙΣΑΡ, *RPC I*, 5295). These coin types reproduce the obverse and reverse images respectively of the first imperial tetradrachms of Egypt, struck under Tiberius in his regnal years 7 (AD 20/21), 14 and 18-23. The standard types of all these coins were the right-facing laureate portrait of ΤΙΒΕΡΙΟΣ ΚΑΙΣΑΡ ΣΕΒΑΣΤΟΣ on the obverse and the right-facing radiate head of the ΘΕΟΣ ΣΕΒΑΣΤΟΣ on the reverse.^[39]

Erik Christiansen, who published a two-volume work on the Alexandrian coinage of the emperors Nero, Trajan and Septimius Severus, was very clear about what he wanted to prove: "The *main thesis* of this book is that the Roman government in AD 63/64 (Nero's 10th regnal year in Egypt) began striking debased billon coins on a vast scale – total estimate for years 10-14 is c. 600 million – to withdraw the older, better Roman billon and Ptolemaic silver coins, and that the purpose not only was to reap a profit of silver, but to send it to Rome in order to relieve Nero's financial difficulties."^[40] Hence, in Christiansen's view, the considerable upsurge in tetradrachm production under Nero was the result of a large-scale reminting. Metallurgical evidence for the fineness of the Egyptian billon tetradrachms of the first centuries BC and AD now is much better than it was in Christiansen's days, and the data we currently have confirm that there was a considerable drop in fineness from Late Ptolemaic to Tiberian and to Neronian times: tetradrachms of Cleopatra VII (51-30 BC) apparently contained about one third of silver,^[41] while the pieces of Tiberius were produced from an alloy of about a quarter fine.^[42] The earlier tetradrachms of Nero (years 3-6) established a new reduced standard of about 19% of silver bullion,^[43] and for the phase of intense minting in years 10-14 another slight reduction is in evidence; the average of the fineness of the coins of these years recently analysed was just 16.8% of silver bullion.^[44]

Hence, Christiansen's hypothesis a priori seems to be backed up by the development of the silver alloy of the issues in question: melting down Ptolemaic and earlier Julio-Claudian issues would certainly have enabled the Neronian administration to profit considerably. Also, the melting down of old tetradrachms under Nero seems to explain why the expression "Ptole-

[39] *RPC I*, p. 696-698.

[40] Christiansen 1988, vol. 1, p. 308; see also pp. 104-106 and 109.

[41] Gölitzler 2004, p. 124; Butcher & Ponting 2014, p. 614.

[42] Gölitzler 2004, p. 125; Butcher & Ponting 2014, p. 617f.

[43] Butcher & Ponting 2014, p. 633.

[44] *Ibid.*, p. 641.

maic money” is attested in the papyri from Egypt only up to AD 64.^[45] Andrew Burnett and Michel Amandry, the authors of the relevant part of *RPC I*, published just a few years after Christiansen’s study, subscribed to his “*main thesis*” and reinforced it with a *prima facie* very attractive typological argument, related to the tetradrachm types described above: “the curious appearance of Tiberius on the coinage together with Divus Augustus can be best explained by reference to the constant type used on the tetradrachms of Tiberius’s reign. Hoards and papyri indicate that earlier tetradrachms were demonetised in the early sixties. [...] It is possible that these coins were issued to retain the images of the emperors in circulation, rather like restored issues...”.^[46]

This interpretation of the evidence may appear convincing in a theoretical perspective, but it does not seem to be supported by modern metallurgical data. According to the research by Kevin Butcher & Matthew Ponting, “trace elements [*sc.* in the Neronian tetradrachms of years 10-14] do not support the idea” of a recoinage of Ptolemaic silver under Nero – although Butcher & Ponting acknowledge that this judgement is based on an extremely small sample, *viz.* just two tetradrachms of Cleopatra VII, which contained significantly less gold than the issues of Nero they analysed.^[47] However, on the basis of a somewhat bigger set of data they note that “there is no compositional evidence to support the recycling of Tiberian tetradrachms into coins of Nero, particularly those of year 13, which bear portraits of Tiberius and Divus Augustus” and therefore conclude that “the fates of the Ptolemaic silver and the Tiberian tetradrachms remain unresolved”, while cautiously proposing that the older coins may have been recycled before Nero already, whose “silver appears to have come from different sources”.^[48] Hence, Butcher & Ponting see themselves forced to completely reject Christiansen’s reconstruction of events. Future analyses may throw more light on the problem.

Another case for which a large-scale coinage renewal has been proposed is the Syrian tetradrachm coinage of Trajan in the COS V and COS VI periods. During (or a short time before) Trajan’s TR P XIV (AD 109/110), when the production of dated series running down to the end of his reign (TR P XXI) started, a reform of the Syrian silver coinage is in evidence. There was a change in style – from the Roman style that had characterised most issues up to the fifth consulate to an eastern style, dubbed “Antioch style” in the literature –, and also a typological diversification: in addition to the tetradrachms featuring the bust of Melqart-Hercules on the reverse, series with an eagle standing on a club and with the old Augustan tetradrachm type of

[45] See Christiansen 1984, p. 295, nos. 56 and 57: P. Yale I 63 (17 July AD 64) and P. Vindob. Tandem 22 (29 November AD 64; no pertinent documents published since 1984 postdate the latter papyrus – thanks to Thomas Kruse for checking); Christiansen 1988, vol. 1, p. 104.

[46] *RPC I*, p. 705.

[47] Butcher & Ponting 2014, p. 644.

[48] All quotations: Butcher & Ponting 2014, p. 644.

the Tyche of Antioch seated right with the river-god Orontes were struck,^[49] all at the same mint.^[50] Most importantly, the silver standard was reduced, and these three copious tetradrachm series were produced from an alloy of about 50% silver and 50% copper.^[51] The coinage was issued in spectacular quantities: on the basis of a die-study, Michel Amandry recently calculated the use of more than 800 obverse dies for these local-style tetradrachms from their inception to the end of Trajan's reign.^[52]

D.R. Walker was the first to detect a change in standards for these series, although he overestimated the silver content in the alloy due to the inadequate sampling technique he used. Walker suggested that the huge output of Trajanic (and early Hadrianic) tetradrachms, which seems to have peaked during Trajan's TR P XV (AD 110/111),^[53] may have been connected with a large-scale withdrawal and reminting of earlier Syrian tetradrachms in this period.^[54] Richard McAlee sounded a note of caution regarding this theory by citing an unpublished Syrian tetradrachm hoard of the later second century that he had examined: it contained first-century material that apparently continued to circulate alongside Trajan's debased issues.^[55] Hence, if Trajan's Antioch-style issues represent a recoinage of earlier tetradrachms, the withdrawal cannot have been complete – but then a comprehensive removal of earlier coinage would have been extremely hard to accomplish anyway. In any case, Walker's hypothesis was in general received positively by McAlee, who pointed out that it might also explain the revival of earlier reverse types under Trajan, especially the Tyche of Antioch, previously used on tetradrachms under Augustus.^[56] The authors of *RPC III*, Michel Amandry and Andrew Burnett, were unsure regarding the validity of Walker's theory of a massive recoinage in Syria under Trajan and pointed out that alternative explanations of the soaring production should not be excluded.^[57]

[49] For these series, see Butcher 2004, p. 87–91; McAlee 2007, pp. 187–191 and 200–205; *RPC III*, p. 455–462.

[50] *RPC III*, p. 445.

[51] Butcher 2004, p. 199.

[52] Amandry 2013, p. 845.

[53] Thus McAlee 2007, p. 191.

[54] Walker 1977, p. 104f.; cp. 105: “The coinage of Trajan and Hadrian from c. 108 to 119 was by far the largest so far produced in Roman Syria and doubtless represents a major recoinage of earlier and finer coins after the debasement”.

[55] McAlee 2007, p. 191 with note 29.

[56] *Ibid.*, p. 191.

[57] Amandry 2013, p. 847f.: “Il y a donc eu, fin 108/début 109, une manipulation monétaire, avec probablement un rappel des espèces antérieures. Comme le disait déjà Walker, c’[...]est [...] la baisse du taux de fin qui a fait s’envoler la production. Mais, bien entendu, d’autres explications sont possibles, dont le paiement de taxes.”; see also *RPC III*, p. 806: “But this (sc. Walker’s) explanation is not supported by any direct evidence of the calling in of earlier pieces.”

The parallels to the case of Nero's Egyptian tetradrachms of years 10-14, discussed above, are clear: both are coinages of considerable volume, whose silver fineness is lower than that of the preceding issues; both revive characteristic earlier reverse types of the same series. However, in the absence of new metallurgical data for the trace element signature of Trajan's new tetradrachms it is not possible to affirm that their metal really was won by melting down older Syrian tetradrachms. As the case of Egypt under Nero shows, such hypotheses may become questionable very quickly in the light of scientific evidence; of course a representative sample is indispensable, if the conclusions drawn from metallurgical analyses are to be meaningful.

Large-scale reminting has been postulated for the Roman provincial bronze coinage as well. Ann Johnston submitted that the base metal coinage of Asia Minor may potentially have gone through two waves of reminting, although she stressed that there is currently no hard and fast evidence to back up her assumption: "I suspect, but cannot prove, that there was large-scale reminting in Asia Minor around 200 and again around 260";^[58] the first wave should have been occasioned by the production of coins for Septimius Severus and family at around 250 civic mints – the all-time peak number of coin producing cities in Asia Minor –, the second by the large issues struck by some cities for Gallienus and Salonina. In both instances, Johnston's suspicions were triggered simply by the sheer volume of new coinage issued in the respective periods; future research may prove her right or wrong.

In cases where a coinage renewal was put into effect by means of overstriking, we are of course on much firmer ground. The most important episode of overstriking in the Roman provincial silver coinage is constituted by the cistophori of Hadrian. Under this emperor, there are two main groups of cistophoric issues: one, showing an incredible typological diversity, was produced at more than twenty mints in the province of Asia,^[59] while the other, much smaller group originates from Bithynia, where it was struck at two different minting establishments. All the Bithynian cistophori bear the same obverse legend in the dative case, *viz.* IMP CAES TRA HADRIANO AVG P P. While one Bithynian sub-group invariably shows the temple of the Bithynian *koinon* in Nicomedia on the reverse, identified as such by the legend COM(mune) BIT(hyniae),^[60] the other, quite rare sub-group – called 'COS III' group in scholarship, in view of a recurring reverse legend – displays greater variety regarding the reverse design.^[61] These two sub-groups are obviously the product of two different Bithynian mints; their coins seem to show a slight difference in weight: the COM BIT sub-group is a little heavier.^[62]

^[58] Johnston 2007, p. 12.

^[59] *RPC III*, p. 165-180.

^[60] *Ibid.*, 968-984.

^[61] *Ibid.*, 960-967.

^[62] See *RPC III*, p. 119 (mean weights 10.51 g *vs* 10.22 g).

These Hadrianic issues were the first cistophori to be produced in Bithynia, while his issues from the province of Asia stand in a long tradition of cistophoric tetradrachms struck by the Roman authorities there since Republican times.^[63] However, Hadrian's coins stand out: while the cistophori of the emperors before him – Augustus, Claudius, the Flavians, Nerva and his predecessor Trajan^[64] – are never found overstruck, Hadrian's Asian cistophori apparently always are. They are the product of the most impressive operation of overstriking in the history of Roman provincial silver coinage.

The cistophori of Hadrian were studied in detail by W.E. Metcalf, who published a die-study almost forty years ago.^[65] In the meantime, a lot of new types have emerged; the entire material is now conveniently assembled in *RPC III*.^[66] Metcalf dated the re-coinage to AD 128-130, a dating to which the authors of *RPC* subscribe:^[67] it seems to have been inaugurated around the time when Hadrian visited Asia Minor on his second journey through the eastern provinces of the empire.^[68] The overstriking was executed mainly on Asian cistophori of Mark Antony and Augustus,^[69] which had been in circulation for between c. 150 and 170 years at the time of restriking. Since the overstriking was done extremely carelessly, traces of the undertypes are visible on most pieces; see, e.g., a piece overstruck on a cistophorus of Mark Antony in fig. 5: remains of the Antonian obverse legend, *COS DESIG ITER*, are in evidence next to and on Hadrian's head, and the legend *III VIR*, as well as large part of a snake, at the temple of Artemis on the reverse. According to Metcalf, no fewer than c. 36% of the undertypes may be assigned at least to an issuer.^[70] This was a huge recoinage: based on the figures that emerged from Metcalf's die counts, the authors of *RPC* recently calculated a total of 729 obverse dies used for the restriking.^[71]

As opposed to Hadrian's cistophori struck in the province of Asia, his Bithynian cistophori described above normally do not display clear signs of undertypes.^[72] Especially the coins of the *COM BIT* sub-group were ob-

[63] For the early Roman cistophori of Asia, see the recent monograph by Metcalf 2017.

[64] On the cistophori of Nerva and Trajan, see the study by Woytek 2010b.

[65] Metcalf 1980.

[66] *RPC III*, 1321-1484; see also the addenda, online at <<http://rpc.ashmus.ox.ac.uk/supp/rpc-sup-4.pdf>> [last accessed on 29 April 2018].

[67] Metcalf 1980, p. 123; *RPC III*, p. 165.

[68] Weber 1907, p. 211-231.

[69] *RPC I*, 2201-2220; very rarely, cistophori of Claudius were overstruck, too (*RPC I*, 2221-2225) For the undertypes, see Metcalf 1980, p. 115f.

[70] Metcalf 1980, p. 115, table 2 (identification possible for 166 of 463 specimens). The carelessness of the Hadrianic moneyers is also evident from specimens overstruck on old cistophori bearing a Flavian countermark that was not obliterated by the overstriking, see e.g. *CNG 70* (21/IX/2005), 988 and 1001 or Gemini 2 (11/II/2006), 392.

[71] *RPC III*, p. 165.

[72] Cp. the statement by Mattingly in *BMC III*, p. clxi: "unlike the certain Asiatic" cistophori, they are "never overstruck on earlier coins".

viously struck on newly made flans. Metcalf explained this by suggesting that the Hadrianic issue introduced this coinage to the province: “since cistophori had never before circulated in Bithynia a fresh coinage was necessary”.^[73]

Fig. 5 – Hadrian, cistophorus, Ephesus (overstruck on cistophorus of Mark Antony). RPC III, 1333 (undertype: RPC I, 2201f.). CNG Electronic Auction 146 (23/VIII/2006), 187 (10.96 g – 30 mm)

scale 200%

However, he recorded a single specimen of the smaller, typologically heterogeneous Bithynian COS III sub-group that doubtless is overstruck on a cistophorus of Augustus.^[74] Metcalf tried to explain away the existence of this overstrike by surmising that the coin had been restruck “by accident”,^[75] but new evidence indicates that this will probably not do. Two specimens of the same sub-group that recently surfaced in the coin trade show traces of overstriking as well: a piece featuring the personification of Bithynia on the

^[73] Metcalf 1980, p. 140.

^[74] *Ibid.*, p. 135, no. 38 (= SNG von Aulock 6611: rev. COS III, bundle of grain stalks).

^[75] *Ibid.*, p. 137, note 1.

reverse,^[76] on which the undertype unfortunately cannot be made out, and a hitherto unpublished type showing a galley with the legend FELICITATI AVGVSTI on the reverse, inspired by one of Hadrian's most distinctive reverses of the imperial coinage (fig. 6).^[77]

This unique cistophorus, which comes from an obverse die already attested on another coin of the group^[78] and, to this author's eye, does not look unauthentic on the images available, was overstruck on a cistophorus of Augustus with the temple of Mars Ultor on the reverse;^[79] in the right field of the Hadrianic coin's reverse the three letters VLT are clearly discernible, as well as a column next to the V, and the temple steps below.

Fig 6 – Hadrian, cistophorus, uncertain Bithynian mint (overstruck on a cistophorus of Augustus with MART – VLTQ). Unpublished (undertype: RPC I, 2220).

Lanz 164 (23/V/2017), 184 (10.80 g – ↑↑ – 29 mm)

scale 200%

[76] RPC III, 960, where this specimen is cited from Gemini 2 (11/I/2006), 401 (10.55 g); it came up for sale again in Stack's Bowers Galleries (& Ponterio) 174 (11/I/2013), 5131.

[77] Lanz 164 (23/V/2017), 184 (10.80 g) = Roma Numismatics E-sale 45 (5/V/2018), 422 (10.80 g – ↑↑ – 29 mm). For the galley in Hadrian's imperial coinage, see Strack 1933, p. 135 and nos. 235-236, 324, 337-339, 667 and 837-844.

[78] RPC III, 963 (rev. Fortuna seated to the left; unique).

[79] RPC I, 2220 (rev. legend MART – VLTQ).

Hence, a pattern seems to be emerging here: the smaller of the two Bithynian groups of cistophori was apparently (in part?) produced by overstriking as well. One should not a priori exclude the possibility that the circulation of cistophori was not limited to the province of Asia before Hadrian, but that these coins had eventually come to be used in the whole of western Asia Minor, in the course of the first and early second centuries AD.^[80] In that perspective, the (partial?) production of one of the groups of Bithynian cistophori by means of overstriking would not be too surprising.

What were the reasons for restriking probably millions of old cistophori mainly in the province of Asia, but to some extent also in Bithynia? David R. Walker was convinced that the purpose of the entire operation should have been to make profit for the Roman state or the mint cities and hypothesised that through the Hadrianic recoinage the cistophori were re-tariffed from three to four denarii each.^[81] He went on to postulate that the restriking “may well have played a part in providing the funds for the enormous building programmes which took place in Asia at this time, as well as producing a general, albeit temporary, increase in the level of prosperity”.^[82] This explanation certainly is alluring,^[83] but most probably wrong. The counterargument which I regard as decisive in this respect has already been stated:^[84] if the restruck cistophori were really worth four denarii, from Hadrian onwards, what about the value of the cistophori of Claudius that were very rarely overstruck, or the cistophori of the Flavians, of Nerva and Trajan, that never were? Since Walker only ever refers to “the cistophori of Hadrian” as being re-tariffed, in the passage of his work in question,^[85] one would have to surmise that, according to his reconstruction, non-overstruck pieces that were in circulation retained their original value – but it is easy to see that this would have led to a chaotic situation in the marketplace. Hence, Walker’s theory should require the assumption of a re-tariffing of all the cistophori in circulation: but why then bother to restrike the coins of Mark Antony and Augustus? All in all, Walker’s explanation must be considered a dead end.

The true purpose of the restriking should instead have been to restore a fresh appearance to masses of old, badly worn money that had been circulating for one and a half centuries and more, as Metcalf has argued.^[86] Of course the problem was not primarily aesthetic, but economic: there is ancient evidence proving that, unsurprisingly, freshly struck coin (*nummus asper*) was preferred in the Roman world.^[87] In some contexts, payment in

[80] See Woytek 2010B, p. 95f. for a few pieces of evidence pointing in this direction.

[81] Walker 1977, p. 64.

[82] *Ibid.*

[83] It was accepted by Howgego 1985, p. 53.

[84] Metcalf 1980, p. 120, note 11 (with reference to previous bibliography).

[85] Walker 1977, p. 64.

[86] See Metcalf 1980, p. 119f., as well as Metcalf 2011, p. 43.

[87] See the exhaustive treatment by Metcalf 1980, p. 119.

new coins was required;^[88] also, sometimes worn coins seem to have been discounted by professional bankers, as compared to freshly minted ones, as the famous rescript from Pergamum implies.^[89] To sum up, restriking the very worn cistophori revalidated them for circulation, and the operation certainly provided a most valuable service to coin users in Asia minor; the initiative as such may possibly be interpreted in the context of Hadrian's munificence towards the province. Of course recoinage of the huge quantities of cistophori was much cheaper and easier than melting them down and producing new flans – it allowed for a renewal of the coinage at minimal cost. As Metcalf pointed out, decentralising the production of Hadrian's cistophori will perhaps also have had practical reasons: overstriking the coins locally made it possible to turn around greater quantities in a shorter time.^[90] Even the most cursory overview over the reverse types of the Hadrianic cistophori shows that the opportunity to place special emphasis on local cults was eagerly seized by those responsible for the coin designs at the various mints. However, the diffusion of these often curious and highly varied images was of course only a secondary consequence of the massive recoinage, not its primary purpose.^[91]

It seems that two of the best-known cistophorus types of Hadrian need to be viewed against the background of the Hadrianic recoinage: the only two types featuring on their obverse a portrait not of Hadrian (or his wife Sabina), but the right-facing head of the first princeps, accompanied by the legend IMP CAESAR AVGVSTVS. On the reverse of these coins, overstruck on old cistophori, too, Hadrian is shown in the toga, either holding grain-stalks in his right hand (*RPC* 1441, fig. 7) or, on a rare variety that turned up fairly recently, after the publication of Metcalf's corpus, sacrificing to the left over a tripod, *capite velato* (*RPC* 1442, fig. 8).

The reverse inscription of both types is HADRIANVS AVG P P REN. The expansion of the last word is not immediately obvious and has given rise to three diverging interpretations of these extraordinary coins. The first theory was formulated at a time when only the variety with Hadrian holding grain-stalks was known: it proposes to expand REN to "*renatus*", and explains the type in the context of Hadrian's (somewhat problematic) initiation into the Eleusinian mysteries, apparently as the first Roman princeps after August-

[88] See, most notably, Suet. Nero 44.2 (*exegitque ingenti fastidio et acerbitate nummum asperum, argentum pustulatum, aurum ad obrussam*); cp. also *IGR* IV 494 (Pergamum) and *IGR* IV 595 (Cadi).

[89] *OGIS* 484 = *IGR* IV 352.

[90] Metcalf 1980, p. 120.

[91] Contrast the positions of Herzfelder 1936, p. 2f. ("Perhaps it was here intended to encourage the worship of the Graeco-Roman divinities by showing them on the main silver currency of the province, in order to spread a wider knowledge of their cults, which were particularly dear to Hadrian", p. 3), Woodward 1956, p. 165, and Metcalf 1980, p. 120.

tus,^[92] after which he was thought to have proclaimed his ‘rebirth’ to eternal life. This explanation of the coins proved very popular; apart from Mattingly,^[93] it was endorsed for example by Dietmar Kienast^[94] and more recently Anthony Birley.^[95] However, it is evident that it only works for the pieces on which Hadrian is holding the grain-stalks, which have been read as a reference to the mysteries of Demeter/Ceres: the newly discovered variety with Hadrian sacrificing at a tripod does not contain any typological link with Eleusis, thereby providing clear proof that the entire concept must be discarded.

Fig. 7 – Hadrian, *cistophorus*, Asia, uncertain mint “C”. RPC III, 1441. CNG Triton 14 (4/1/2011), no. 625 (10.90 g)

Fig. 8 – Hadrian, *cistophorus*, Asia, uncertain mint “C”. RPC III, 1442. CNG 72 (14/VI/2006), no. 1366 (10.74 g)

Hence, Alexander Mlasowsky, in a comprehensive article, proposed a new interpretation of these types that is not based exclusively on the grain-stalks: he expands REN to “*renovator*”, proposing that the *cistophori* might depict Hadrian as the new κτίστης of Ephesus,^[96] and commemorate on a more general level the emperor’s benefactions towards Asia Minor as a whole.^[97] However, Mlasowsky’s thesis, recently accepted by Dario Calomino,^[98] clearly fails to adequately explain the most important feature of these coins: the portrait of Augustus on their obverse. Calomino’s attempt to support Mlasowsky’s theory by pointing out that Augustus may be depicted merely as “the model ruler that Hadrian was most keen to emulate”^[99] cannot be regarded as convincing, because it is too simplistic.

[92] On the initiation (reported *inter alios* by Cass. Dio 69.11.1 and HA Hadrian 13.1) and the problems surrounding it see Fündling 2006, vol. 2, p. 627–630.

[93] BMC III, p. clxi.

[94] Kienast 1959/60.

[95] Birley 1997, p. 215f.

[96] He points to the inscription *Inschriften griechischer Städte aus Kleinasien (IK)*, vol. 12 (Ephesus), part II (Bonn 1979), no. 274 = Smallwood 1966, no. 494 (AD 129), where Hadrian is referred to as the city’s κτίστης and σωτήρ in line 8, in view of his support on various levels, including the supply of grain from Egypt.

[97] Mlasowsky 2011, p. 101–103.

[98] Calomino 2015, p. 71f.

[99] *Ibid.*, p. 72.

The interpretation of these coin types that I believe to be the correct one has been given by W.E. Metcalf: he expands the word REN to “*renovavit*” and connects the legends of these coins with the renewal of the cistophoric coinage by Hadrian. The decisive merit of this reading and understanding of the inscription is that it makes sense of both sides of the Hadrianic coins. As already pointed out by Metcalf,^[100] their obverse legend IMP CAESAR AVGVSTVS is a combination of the obverse and reverse legends of the vast majority of the cistophorus types of Augustus;^[101] the obverse of Hadrian’s coins thus reproduces the main type and the legends of a significant part of the coins that were ‘renewed’ in the course of Hadrian’s large-scale operation of overstriking. Thereby, designs that were obliterated on the overstruck coins were preserved on the special series featuring Augustus. Hadrian himself is shown on the reverse, sacrificing as the pious successor of Augustus, whom he held in veneration,^[102] and holding out corn-ears as the patron of the cities of Asia minor, to which he had granted the considerable favour of renewing their silver coinage.^[103] These cistophori were not strictly speaking ‘restored’ coins – such issues bear the word REST(ituit) in their reverse legend –, but may be considered to be a closely related phenomenon.^[104]

Another case of two groups of provincial silver coins of the High Empire that were, at least in part, produced by overstriking may be dealt with somewhat more concisely here, since it has been discussed at length by Kevin Butcher and this author elsewhere.^[105] It differs in two important points from the case of Hadrian’s overstruck cistophori: the denomination of the coins (drachms, not tetradrachms) and the issuing authority of the undertype (foreign, not Roman).

After the occupation of the Nabataean kingdom and its integration into the Roman Empire as the new province of Arabia in AD 106, Trajan also had to deal with one specific monetary problem: Arabia needed a new Roman provincial silver coinage. The country had been using the Nabataean royal coinage prior to the annexation; the last Nabataean king Rabbel II (AD 70/1–105/6), whose coins have recently been studied in depth,^[106] struck in silver and bronze: the highest silver denomination – and at the same time almost the only one that was produced – was the drachm, with extremely rare halves and quarters struck just at the beginning of his reign.^[107] Under Trajan, no

[100] Metcalf 1980, p. 90.

[101] *RPC I*, 2204–2215 (IMP CAESAR: obverse; AVGVSTVS: reverse).

[102] Cp. the denarii *RIC I²* Augustus 208, with Woytek & Blet-Lemarquand 2017, p. 223–225.

[103] This interpretation was also preferred by the authors of *RPC III*, pp. 176 and 848.

[104] They have been identified as such already by Gnechchi 1897, p. 154f.

[105] See Woytek & Butcher 2015 and Butcher & Woytek 2018.

[106] Barkay 2014.

[107] Barkay 2014, p. 30. As for the bronze, two denominations (medium and small) were produced under Rabbel II, see Barkay 2014, p. 36.

bronzes were issued in or for Arabia, but just silver coins with Greek legends: multiples of the drachm, variously identified as tridrachms or (light) tetradrachms, with various reverse types that were produced in the COS V and COS VI periods of Trajan's rule,^[108] and two groups of COS VI drachms of completely different styles and types. These drachms are in the focus of our analysis, since they were, at least partly, overstruck on Nabataean drachms.

The two groups of drachms were struck in different periods of Trajan's sixth consulship. The first group is of the rather crude 'Antioch style' that we have already encountered above, in dealing with Trajan's Syrian tetradrachms of the period. These Arabian drachms show the personification of the new province of Arabia on the reverse, a design that had been used on imperial coins of Trajan struck at Rome from the later COS V period onwards.^[109] There are three consecutive issues of these Arabia drachms, dated in the legends to Trajan's sixth consulship (AD 112-117) and his 16th, 17th and 18th tribunician powers respectively,^[110] equivalent to the years AD 111/112, 112/113 and 113/114.^[111] Trajan is not yet styled "Optimus" (ἄριστος) on the last issue of these drachms, which means that the group as such must date to the months between 1 January 112 and spring (June?) 114.^[112] That these coins are sometimes found overstruck on Nabataean drachms has been known since the early 1970s, when Avraham Negev published some specimens of this kind from the large Mampsis hoard that clearly show Nabataean letters as remains of the undertype;^[113] material that turned up subsequently fully confirmed his observations (cp. fig. 9).^[114]

Fig. 9 – Trajan, drachm, struck at uncertain eastern mint for circulation in Arabia, TR P XVI COS VI = AD 112 (overstruck on a Nabataean drachm: traces of letters in left rev. field). *RPC III*, 4073. *Münz Zentrum Rheinland* 116 (7/VI/2003), 359 (3.21 g), ex *Schenk-Behrens* 83 (23/VI/2002), 238

From the period AD 18-21 down to the end of the independent kingdom, Nabataean drachms had constantly been produced from an alloy of about

[108] *RPC III*, 4050-4071; Woytek 2010B, p. 111-120. On the question of denomination, see the discussion in *RPC III*, p. 529f.

[109] See Woytek 2010A, nos. 285 (denarii), 290 (aurei), 362-365 (bronzes) etc.

[110] *RPC III*, 4072-4075.

[111] Under Trajan the TR P was renewed on 10 December.

[112] On the problem of dating Trajan's assumption of the name "Optimus" see Burnett 2017.

[113] Negev 1971.

[114] See Woytek & Butcher 2015, p. 131-132.

50% silver and 50% copper.^[115] This is the very same standard that was used for Trajan's drachms with Arabia on the reverse, as metallurgical analyses have shown,^[116] and already David Walker rightly concluded that "the whole purpose of these issues was to recoin the debased and miserable coinage of the Nabataean kingdom which had been annexed by Trajan in 106".^[117] It is not clear whether the entire group or just part of it was produced by overstriking. However, perhaps one should not exclude that all the Trajanic Arabia drachms were overstruck, and that the Romans did not produce any new flans for these coins, for the following reason: the diameter of the Nabataean coins, which were struck on thickish flans, is significantly smaller than the diameter of the Roman drachms; as per Rachel Barkay, drachms of Rabbel II mostly measure between *c.* 12 and *c.* 16 mm,^[118] whereas Trajan's Arabia drachms have a diameter of *c.* 19–20 mm.^[119] Hence, Avraham Negev proposed that the Nabataean coins may have been hammered flat before they were restruck, so that the undertype would have been obliterated at least partly already before the Trajanic images were applied.^[120] Of course the restriking itself will then have eliminated any and all remains of the original design in most cases. This means that traces of the undertype survived only very rarely on these issues, in view of the two-step production technique. For this reason, I believe that it is by no means impossible that all of Trajan's Arabia drachms were overstruck. Where the Nabataean coins that the Romans used to produce their drachms came from is open to conjecture: Negev hypothesised that the Roman authorities may have re-issued local coinage they seized as part of the Nabataean royal treasure after the annexation in AD 106,^[121] but in view of the fact that the production of the Trajanic drachms started only six years later, it is equally possible that the coins were drawn from circulation. Where exactly the overstriking was performed is not completely clear either, but a mint somewhere in Syria is extremely likely.^[122]

The second group of Trajanic drachms circulating in Arabia was struck immediately after production of the coins featuring the personification of the province had been discontinued. In their obverse legend Trajan is already called ἄριστος, but he does not yet bear the *cognomen virtutis* Παρθικός; hence these coins must have been produced between spring AD 114 and February 116, when the emperor assumed the name "Parthicus". These drachms depict a two-humped Bactrian camel on their reverses and were struck from

[115] Thus Schmitt-Korte & Cowell 1989, p. 56f.

[116] See Woytek & Butcher 2015, p. 131, note 67 for the references.

[117] Walker 1977, p. 108.

[118] Barkay 2014, p. 41–43.

[119] *RPC* III, p. 533f.

[120] Negev 1971, p. 116, with Woytek & Butcher 2015, p. 131.

[121] Negev 1971, p. 117.

[122] See Butcher 2012, p. 209.

dies of a much better style than the Arabia drachms, clearly cut by engravers of the Roman mint.^[123] Three years ago, Kevin Butcher and this author published a Trajanic camel drachm kept in the Kadman Numismatic Pavilion of the Eretz-Israel Museum, Tel Aviv (inv. no. K-2712; fig. 10) that is evidently overstruck on a Nabataean drachm, too. It shows traces of the undertype on both sides: Nabataean letters on the obverse and the back of the Nabataean king's head as well as the ties of his laurel wreath and another letter on the reverse, in the exergue below the camel. The coin is clearly authentic and the product of an official mint;^[124] the Nabataean coin type on which it was overstruck cannot be identified precisely, but specialists in Nabataean coinage concur in attributing it to Rabbel II.^[125]

While this is the only specimen of the issue with clearly identifiable remains of an undertype that has come to my attention, there are several more camel drachms with indistinct traces of overstriking especially in the reverse fields,^[126] which indicates that at least part of the camel group was overstruck on Nabataean drachms, too, just as the preceding Arabia group. However, preparation of the coins to be used as flans was apparently more careful still for the camel drachms, so that remains of the undertypes are extremely rare.

Fig. 10 – Trajan, drachm, struck for circulation in Arabia, AD 114–116 (overstruck on a Nabataean drachm, probably of Rabbel II). RPC III, 4076. Kadman Numismatic Pavilion of the Eretz Israel Museum, Tel Aviv, inv. K-2712 (3.40 g); published and discussed by Woytek & Butcher 2015. Photo © Eretz Israel Museum

scale 200%

[123] RPC III, 4076–4081.

[124] It is a double die-duplicate of the specimen ANS 1956.127.2241 from the Tell Kalak hoard.

[125] See Woytek & Butcher 2015, p. 133.

[126] For a listing, see Woytek & Butcher 2015, p. 134.

Unsurprisingly, the new overstrike ties in well with data on the metallurgy of these coins that is available from previous analyses of other specimens: the camel drachms were produced from an alloy of the same type as the Arabia drachms and the late Nabataean royal drachms, consisting of c. 50% silver and c. 50% copper.^[127] Thus, in both groups of drachms struck for Arabia, Trajan's financial administration simply continued to use the traditional local coin standard. The identification of the overstruck camel coin raises questions of considerable importance for our understanding of the provincial coinages of the High Principate in general: was this issue of Rome style, which also exhibits a die-axis pattern exactly like Roman denarii of the same period,^[128] really produced at the mint of Rome (which would imply that the Nabataean coins that were to be overstruck would have had to be transported to Italy from Arabia)? Or were rather the dies for this issue shipped from Rome to the east, where overstriking was more common than in the capital? Both options seem conceivable, and so far it has not been possible to definitively rule out one or the other.^[129]

Fortunately, we can keep this problem open in the present context, since the identification of the place where the camel drachms were overstruck is not essential to our argument. The Trajanic drachms produced for Arabia make for a most interesting case study in a bigger perspective anyway: for the Principate, this seems to be the earliest instance in which the Roman state converted foreign coin into Roman by means of overstriking. Hoard evidence from the Hadrianic period makes it clear that Nabataean coinage continued to circulate (or, more precisely, to be saved) alongside the new Trajanic Roman provincial issues; the Roman state by no means seems to have decreed a demonetisation of the royal coins.^[130] Still, it was felt necessary to give the drachm coinage of the province a Roman appearance, perhaps in order to bring it in line with the multiple drachms that were introduced to the region by Trajan as a new denomination. Since the drachms of Rabbel II were by no means very old when they were restruck, the operation of overstriking conducted under Trajan was apparently not primarily dictated by economic necessities; juridical aspects – new Roman coinage on new Roman territory? – may have played a part, but I doubt that they were decisive. Perhaps it is not unreasonable to suppose that the aspect of Roman self-fashioning was instrumental in the decision to re-issue Nabataean drachms in a Trajanic guise.

In this context, the best-documented operation of overstriking of the Hadrianic era apart from the cistophoric re-coinage must be mentioned: the overstrikes of the Bar Kochba Revolt (AD 132-135). The silver coins of the rebels, issued in two denominations (*sela* = tetradrachm; *zuz* = drachm), were

[127] Woytek & Butcher 2015, p. 133f.

[128] See Woytek & Butcher 2015, p. 124f. on this point.

[129] For a discussion of these problems, see Woytek & Butcher 2015, p. 134-136, as well as Butcher & Woytek 2018.

[130] See Woytek & Butcher 2015, p. 130 (on the Murraba'ât hoard).

without exception overstruck on earlier, usually Roman, coins. Especially among the drachm undertypes, Trajanic coins feature prominently. It is significant that the rebels manifestly did not select coins of certain standards of fineness for overstriking, but indiscriminately restruck coins that were of the right size, whether imperial denarii, produced from a silver alloy of 80% or 90%, or provincial drachms containing just 50% of silver, like Trajan's Arabian drachms. Both of the Arabian types – with the camel reverse (see fig. 11) as well as with the Arabia reverse – are among the series overstruck by the Jewish rebels. Hence, at least part of the respective coins restruck by Bar Kochba's moneyers will have undergone a double transformation, in two consecutive operations of overstriking: first from Nabataean to Roman, under Trajan, and then from Roman to Jewish, during the revolt.

Fig. 11 – Left: Bar Kochba, drachm (zuz), AD 132-135 (overstruck on a drachm of Trajan, rev. camel). Mildenberg 1984, 164.

Depicted right: an example of the overstruck type (RPC III, 4076).

Both coins: *The New York Sale 39* (10/11/2017), 204 (the zuz: 2.98 g)

scale 200%

Leo Mildenberg, who published a meticulous die-study of the coins of the Bar Kochba War, convincingly argued that this coinage was not primarily occasioned by economic considerations: theoretically the Jewish insurgents could have continued to pay with the Roman coins in circulation. Rather, “the real reason for the Bar Kochba coinage emerges from [...] the simple desire for state propaganda”.^[131] The rebels wanted to “publicize loudly and proudly the national and cultural rebirth of the Jewish state”,^[132] and therefore designed their coinage very carefully, by choosing coin types with a

[131] Mildenberg 1984, p. 72; Meshorer 2001, p. 137 concurs: “the main reason for this phenomenon (sc. the coinage of Bar Kochba) was a political one”.

[132] Mildenberg 1984, p. 72.

decidedly nationalist message, accompanied by patriotic slogans in the legends, for which Hebrew was chosen as the language, and – especially telling – the archaic Palaeo-Hebrew as the script. The Jewish words and images were stamped over the types and legends of the Roman emperors. Hence, apart from the economic side, an ‘ideological’ aspect was potentially inherent in programmes of overstriking in the ancient world as well. Additional examples of this may be found in the Roman provincial bronze coinage, to which we shall now turn.

In general, overstriking has been reported for bronze coins of various Roman provincial mints in various periods, to be sure.^[133] For example, according to John Mavrogordato, “an unusual number of all denominations” of the coins of Chios that he attributed to the Julio-Claudian period were “struck over older coins”, although he could not identify any of the undertypes.^[134] J.G. Milne reported overstrikes – similarly on unidentified coins – for colonial bronzes of the mint of Antioch in Pisidia, issued under Gallienus (253-268) and Claudius Gothicus (268-270);^[135] in this case, the phenomenon must be seen in the context of the deplorable style and workmanship of this mint’s coins in the given time frame.

However, there are also several cases in which the undertypes are recognisable: they provide valuable insights into the practice of overstriking in the Roman provincial world. We will briefly mention three pertinent cases here. At the mint of Smyrna, an unusual issue without imperial heads was produced in the names of Ti. Claudius Sosandros (as *strategos*) and Ti. Claudius Hieronymos, in the first century AD, in three denominations (*RPC I*, 2487-2491). The two types of the middle denomination of this large ‘pseudo-autonomous’ issue, which were produced in much greater quantities than the larger and smaller pieces, show a draped bust of the Senate and a temple front (*RPC* 2489), and Nemesis standing to the right and a reclining river god (*RPC* 2490) respectively. When Dietrich Klose prepared the corpus of the imperial coinage of Smyrna, he noticed that these coins sometimes bear clear traces of overstriking. Klose recognised coins of Nero from the same mint as undertypes in three cases (cp. fig. 12, where the back of Nero’s head is visible underneath the river god on the reverse). He was therefore able to correct

[133] Imhoof-Blumer 1898, p. 3f. drew attention to the fact that many of the undated bronze coins of Eusebeia (later Caesarea) were overstruck on bronzes of Apamea in Phrygia; on the date of these coins see now Kovacs 2013, p. 398f. (c. 66-54/3 BC). These coins have not been included in *RPC I* (cp. p. 552) and also fall outside the chronological scope of our paper.

[134] Mavrogordato 1918, p. 11. For a critical discussion of the – sometimes problematic – chronology proposed by Mavrogordato, see *RPC I*, p. 409f.

[135] Milne 1947, p. 100 and especially 102: “the later series of Gallienus and the coins of Claudius are generally restruck on earlier pieces: the traces of previous types are not sufficiently clear to enable them to be exactly identified, but it is evident that the flans were old ones”. Krzyżanowska 1970, p. 82-84 confirms this and discusses the problem which coins may have been overstruck, although, like Milne, she was unable to identify any undertypes with certainty.

the dating of the issue of Sosandros and Hieronymos – which had previously been attributed to the time of Tiberius – to the period after Nero’s death.^[136]

Fig. 12 – Smyrna, bronze, Ti. Claudius Sosandros (as strategos) and Ti. Claudius Hieronymos, c. AD 68/69 (overstruck on a bronze coin of Nero from Smyrna).
 RPC I, 2490 (undertype: RPC I, 2483f.); Klose 1987, p. 137, no. 87.
 KHM Vienna, inv. GR 17689 (4.91 g – 17). Photo © Klaus Vondrovec

scale 200%

The authors of *RPC* identified a further undertype on pieces, where Klose simply had seen traces of overstriking; a coin of Caligula, again from the mint of Smyrna (probably *RPC* 2471, see also 2472):^[137] cp. fig. 13, where on the obverse, at 6 o’clock, the letters ΑΟΥΙΟ (to be read outwardly) are in evidence, part of the dating ΕΠΙ ΑΟΥΙΟΛΑ on the obverse of the undertype, referring to the proconsul of Asia C. Calpurnius Aviola, who held office in AD 37/38.^[138]

It is, of course, tempting to speculate that the undertypes identified so far are not by chance coins of the only two Julio-Claudian emperors who fell victim to a *damnatio memoriae*. Indeed, Ann Johnston suspected that their coins were deliberately withdrawn from circulation in Smyrna and restruck in the form of the middle denomination of this abnormally large, clearly atypical pseudo-autonomous issue after Nero’s death.^[139] If she is right, the

[136] See Klose 1987, pp. 119 and 137.

[137] See *RPC* I, pp. 418 and 420, type no. 2489, specimen no. 1. I am most grateful to Andrew Burnett for re-examining this specimen at my request.

[138] Stumpf 1991, p. 134f.

[139] See Johnston 1998, p. 156 with note 5; already Klose 1987, p. 119 had explained the Nero overstrikes with reference to this emperor’s *damnatio memoriae*. This case is not discussed by Calomino 2016 (cp. p. 220f.).

authorities of Smyrna would have jumped at the opportunity and tried to wipe the slate clean, after Nero's end, by withdrawing and reminting not only this emperor's coins, but also issues of the similarly damned Caligula.

Fig. 13 – Smyrna, bronze, Ti. Claudius Sosandros (as *strategos*) and Ti. Claudius Hieronymos, c. AD 68/69 (overstruck on a bronze coin of Caligula from Smyrna). *RPC I*, 2489 (undertype: *RPC I*, 2471f.); Klose 1987, p. 134, no. 59. British Museum, London, *BMC Ionia* (Head 1892), Smyrna 122 (5.59 g – 1↑). Photo © The Trustees of the British Museum

scale 200%

As far as Nero is concerned, another episode of overstriking in the provincial area with similar background is to be observed at Sardis. There is a group of three types of Sardian coins without an imperial bust or titulature signed by the *strategos* Ti. Klaudios Phileinos (*RPC II*, 1305-1307), two of which bear the additional indication ἐπὶ Μαρκέλλου Σαρδιανῶν τὸ β: these were produced in the second year of the proconsulship of Ti. Clodius M. f. Eprius Marcellus, who was in office for three years between AD 70/1 and 72/3 and signed coins in several other cities of Asia minor, too.^[140] All the three types almost always show traces of overstriking, and in the cases where undertypes can be identified they turn out to be coins of Nero, either from the mint of Sardis or from Apollonos Hieron.^[141] In publishing two overstruck coins of Eprius Marcellus found in the Sardis excavations, Ann Johnston suggested that this issue should reflect “a policy of withdrawal and overstri-

[140] See Stumpf 1991, p. 190-194.

[141] Cp. the references in *RPC II*, p. 199.

king” on the part of the Sardinian authorities, as coins of Nero “passed through official hands”, after his *damnatio memoriae*.^[142] The obvious “tradition of political interference”^[143] on the local coinage of Sardis, which goes back to the curiously countermarked coins in the name of Germanicus and Drusus minor (fig. 1), discussed above, is striking; it may be mentioned in passing that it seems to have continued after the issue signed by Klaudios Phileinos, too, since overstrikes over coins featuring a ΔOMITI(ANVS) countermark, probably referring to the emperor,^[144] are attested at Sardis under Nerva,^[145] and more overstriking seems to have gone on perhaps under Trajan.^[146]

But, as we may point out in conclusion, ‘political’ overstriking on Roman provincial coinage was by no means confined to first-century AD Asia Minor. In a paper that is otherwise not without problems,^[147] Arie Kindler published two bronze coins of Severus Alexander, produced at the mint of Neapolis in Samaria, featuring Mount Gerizim on the reverse, that were overstruck on colonial coins of Elagabalus, against whom a *damnatio memoriae* had officially been declared after his assassination. One undertype is a coin from Caesarea Maritima bearing a portrait of Elagabalus,^[148] the other is a coin from Sebaste with a portrait of Aquilia Severa, the second wife of Elagabalus.^[149] Of course the local authorities were unable to withdraw all the coins of emperors whose memory had been condemned, but in some cases they seem to have made at least a symbolic effort.

To sum up, overstriking is very rare in the Roman provincial coinage in general. The few episodes that are attested fall into several different groups, according to the different purposes this measure could have: the renewal of Roman coins that had been used for a very long time and were therefore worn out (Hadrian’s restriking of old cistophori); the conversion of foreign coins circulating in newly annexed territory into Roman ones (Trajan’s Arabian drachms, overstruck on Nabataean coins); and finally very uncommon instances of locally circumscribed ‘political’ overstriking, aimed at the obliteration of bronze coin types produced under emperors whose memory had been condemned (e.g. Caligula, Nero and Elagabalus).

[142] See her remarks in Buttrey *et al.* 1981, p. 81f., commentary on no. 247.

[143] Thus RPC II, p. 199.

[144] Howgego 1985, p. 208, no. 533.

[145] RPC III, 239of. For a commentary on the problem of this countermark, see RPC II, p. 198f.

[146] RPC II, 1323 (pseudo-autonomous; for a Trajanic attribution see now RPC III, p. 297).

[147] See Howgego 1985, p. 5f.

[148] Kindler 1980, p. 6, no. 1.

[149] *Ibid.*, no. 2. This coin was republished by Calomino 2016, p. 164, no. 18.

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